

NBR/BENTONITE COMPOSITES: TREATMENT OF THE FILLER ON RHEOMETRIC AND TENSILE PROPERTIES OF NBR/BENTONITE VULCANIZATES

M.N. Ichazo¹, M. Hernández¹, C. Albano², J. González¹, W. De Sousa²

¹Universidad Simón Bolívar, Departamento de Mecánica, Caracas-Venezuela.

²Universidad Central de Venezuela, Escuela de Ingeniería Química, Caracas-Venezuela.

e-mail: michazo@usb.ve / marherna@usb.ve

SUMMARY

Bentonite was added to acrylonitrile–butadiene rubber (NBR) in proportions of 10, 20 and 30 phr. Both, the reinforcing effect and the treatment of the filler with a quaternary amine (octadecylamine), were investigated using rheometric measurements, physico-mechanical properties, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Keywords: Acrylonitrile–butadiene rubber (NBR) vulcanizates, bentonite, nanometric fillers, rheometric properties, mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the wide range of applications Nitrile rubber (NBR) has, especially because of its solvent and oil resistance, there is a tendency to develop new technologies which permit to manufacture products of better quality and performance at lower costs. The addition of reinforcing fillers to elastomers usually conducts to an increase in their mechanical properties and in their abrasion and tear resistance. In particular, carbon black is the reinforcing filler mostly used in rubber vulcanizates. Nonetheless, in the last decades the use of fillers with a color different than black which equally improve the tensile behaviour is increasing. Among them, one can mention the layered clay silicates such as montmorillonite, hectorite, bentonite, etc. which have been used as reinforcing fillers in polymers and elastomers due to their high aspect ratio and because at least one of their dimensions is in the nanometric range [1]. Hishan et al [2] analyzed the use of montmorillonite as reinforcing and compatibilizing filler for NBR/SBR rubber compounds. On the other hand, Gopakumat et al [3] used montmorillonite in polyethylene compounds.

With the aim of improving the interaction between these type of inorganic fillers and elastomers of hydrocarbon nature, different chemical treatments have been practiced to these fillers in order to improve their compatibility with the polymeric matrix. López-Manchado et al [4] investigated blends of natural rubber with clay using as coupling agent bis(trietoxisililpropil) tetrasulfur (TESPT) employing mechanical mixing or intercalation in the molten state and solution mixing.

Jin-Tae et al [5] studied the morphology and the rheometric properties of nanocomposites based on NBR and organomodified silicates. López-Manchado et al [6]

analyzed the effect of the incorporation of an organomodified bentonite on the curing kinetics of natural rubber by means of rheometry and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) under isothermal conditions. Hwang et al [7] investigated the effect of treating layered silicate fillers with a surfactant in order to obtain an exfoliated structure and so improve the mechanical properties of NBR vulcanizates. Also, Yoon et al [8] considered the modification of montmorillonite with amine derivatives with the intention of preparing polymer nanocomposites.

Based on all these previous researches, the present work has the intention of studying the influence of bentonite content (untreated and treated with octadecylamine) on the physical, rheometrical and mechanical properties of Nitrile Rubber, as well as how the ageing process affects those properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Compounds prepared were based on a *KRYNAC* Acrylonitrile-Butadiene rubber (NBR) and an *OPTIBENT CP* sodium bentonite. The curing system employed was based on 100 phr NBR, 3 phr ZnO, 1.5 phr S, 1 phr stearic acid and 0.7 phr of N-t-butyl benzothiazole sulfenamide (TBBS). The bentonite was added in proportions of 10, 20 and 30 phr. The treatment of the filler was done through mixing in aqueous solution with octadecylamine and HCl.

Procedure

Compounds were prepared using a Banbury® internal mixer following the mixing procedure reflected on the ASTM D3568 standard. Cure characteristics were studied using a Rotorless rheometer model EKT-2.000SP according to the ASTM D5289 method. Tensile and tear properties were determined considering the ASTM D412 and ASTM D624 procedures respectively. Morphological studies of cryogenically fractured samples of NBR with bentonite were carried out using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), Hitachi S-2400. Samples were fractured in liquid nitrogen and the surface covered with a thin layer of platinum-palladium.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Rheometric properties

Table 1 shows the rheometric parameters obtained for the NBR formulations without bentonite (NBR00), with 10, 20 and 30 phr of bentonite (B) and with the same proportions of treated filler (TB) for the curing system studied at a temperature of 170 °C. The minimum (M_L) torque, which is proportional to the viscosity of the uncured compound, increases by the addition of the filler; the treatment of the latter increases even more the viscosity of the system. On the other hand, the maximum elastic torque (M_H) values increase with the presence of the bentonite; nonetheless, the rise in this parameter for the formulations with the treated filler is less significant. In general, the no presence of fillers restricts deformation, and consequently, the compound becomes harder and stiffer thereby increasing the torque of the vulcanizates.

Scorch time (ts_2) decreases notoriously when bentonite is used as filler and decreases even more when the treated bentonite is employed probably due to the basic nature of this filler that is potentially increased with the treatment. The time corresponding to 90% of the maximum torque (tc_{90}) increases with respect to the value presented for the unfilled NBR when untreated bentonite is present. All these variations on the values of ts_2 and tc_{90} are in agreement with the results obtained by Hishan et al [2] when montmorillonite was used as reinforcing filler in NBR/SBR rubber blends.

Concerning the treatment of the filler, the results obtained show that for the same filler content, the composites with treated bentonite present a curing time lower (approximately half) than their equivalent formulation with the untreated filler. The rise on the precocity and curing rate index (CRI) is basically due to the fact that when the bentonite is treated, the intercalation of the octadecylamine in the silicate galleries facilitates the curing reaction. The CRI is a parameter proportional to the average slope of the curing rate in the step region ($100/(tc_{90} - ts_2)$). Similar results were obtained by López-Manchado et al [6] when using octadecylamine- modified clay in Natural rubber, which could be attributed to a synergetic effect between the filler and the amine.

Table 1. Rheometric properties of NBR vulcanizates.

Formulation	M_L (dN.m)	M_H (dN.m)	ts_2 (min)	tc_{90} (min)	CRI (s⁻¹)
NBR00	0.27	6.5	2.4	8.2	0.28
NBR10B	0.36	7.7	1.8	11	0.18
NBR20B	0.45	8.8	1.6	11	0.19
NBR30B	0.53	10.3	1.4	11	0.18
NBR10TB	0.39	6.5	1.2	6.4	0.32
NBR20TB	0.53	6.6	1	6.4	0.30
NBR30TB	0.88	7.1	0.7	4.2	0.48

Mechanical properties

Table 2 presents the tensile properties of the vulcanizates. It is possible to observe that, in general, the bentonite in the proportions used acts as a reinforcing filler since it increases the tensile stress at 100% (σ_{100}) and at 300% (σ_{300}) of elongation and the tensile strength and the elongation at break (σ_R and ϵ_R respectively), as well as the tear strength (TS). However, the improvement when the bentonite is treated is far more notorious. It should be mentioned that the bentonite was organically modified through the intercalation with octadecylamine in order to provide it with a hydrophobic nature, thus reducing the surface energy and increasing the interlayer distance. So, the treated

bentonite is more compatible with the rubber, and also, when the separation between silicate layers is increased, the penetration of the elastomer is easily done, thus increasing the polymer-filler interaction and the reinforcing effect of the bentonite as well.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of NBR vulcanizates.

Formulation	σ_{100} (MPa)	σ_{300} (MPa)	σ_R (MPa)	ϵ_R (%)	TS [kN/m]
NBR00	1.1 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.3	421 ± 34	20 ± 1
NBR10B	1.4 ± 0.1	2.8 ± 0.2	3.7 ± 0.3	396 ± 36	25 ± 1
NBR20B	1.4 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.1	5.2 ± 0.5	538 ± 30	34 ± 2
NBR30B	1.7 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.2	426 ± 28	29 ± 2
NBR10TB	1.3 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	8.0 ± 0.8	735 ± 27	33 ± 1
NBR20TB	1.6 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.2	7.8 ± 0.8	667 ± 43	38 ± 3
NBR30TB	2.1 ± 0.1	3.7 ± 0.2	10.8 ± 0.9	730 ± 37	47 ± 2

Morphology

The tendencies obtained on the mechanical properties can be easily understood when we study the morphology of the compounds here studied. Figure 1(a) displays a microphotograph of the NBR30B formulation, where we can clearly see an irregular surface with voids derivatives of the cavitation of the bentonite particles from the elastomeric matrix, after the cryogenic fracture of the samples. This fact could point out that the untreated bentonite has a poor adhesion with the polymer matrix due to its hydrophilic nature.

As a comparison, the morphology of the NBR30BT compound is presented in Figure 1(b). In this case, we can detail a minimum amount of holes, as an indicative of a better adhesion of the treated bentonite to the rubber, thus facilitating the interaction between the filler and the NBR matrix.

CONCLUSIONS

The addition of bentonite to NBR vulcanizates promotes a decrease in the t_s and an increase in the curing time of the vulcanization reaction. However, the treatment of the filler with octadecylamine decreases both parameters, thus considerably increasing the curing index of the NBR. Concerning the mechanical behaviour of these vulcanizates, the results obtained let us consider the bentonite as reinforcing filler for the NBR since

the tensile strength and the tear strength increase. Moreover, the bentonite organically modified through the intercalation with octadecylamine increases even more this tendency due to the greater compatibility with the rubber. One aspect to highlight is the important rise in the elongation at break that all the NBR/TB compounds present with respect to the neat NBR.

Figure 1. SEM microphotographs of: (a) NBR30B, (b) NBR30BT.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank the DID-USB, the technical staff from Laboratorio E-USB, Escuela de Ing. Química de la Universidad Central de Venezuela, IVIC and FONACIT for the financial support through the grant G-2001000817.

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